

UMERC+METS 2024 Conference

7-9 August | Duluth, MN, USA

Review on Recent WEC-Sim Applications and Developments in v6.0

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Abstract

WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) is an open-source software for modeling the motions, loads and power generation of wave energy converters. WEC-Sim is developed within the MATLAB/Simulink environment, which allows for incorporation of different MathWorks packages that are relevant to the offshore renewable energy research community. WEC-Sim performs simulations in the time domain using hydrodynamic coefficients calculated by boundary element method (BEM) frequency-domain potential flow solvers such as WAMIT, NEMOH, Capytaine, or Ansys Aqwa. WEC-Sim development is ongoing, including various features, applications, and example cases used to demonstrate potential use-cases to meet the needs of the growing marine energy industry. In this paper we discuss the new advancement in WEC-Sim v6.0 and WEC-Sim Applications v6.0.

Keywords: Wave energy converter; hydrodynamics modeling; WEC-Sim; power take-off; mooring; and multibody dynamics

1. Introduction

WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter SIMulator) [1] is an open-source tool designed for simulating wave energy converters. Developed in MATLAB/SIMULINK with the multi-body dynamics solver Simscape Multibody, WEC-Sim offers comprehensive modeling capabilities. It can simulate devices comprising various components such as bodies (rigid and flexible), joints, power take-off systems, and mooring systems.

The software operates in the time-domain, solving the wave energy converter's equations of motion across six Cartesian degrees-of-freedom, in addition to any user-defined modes. The WEC-Sim Applications repository [2] showcases a broad array of scenarios, including desalination, mooring dynamics, nonlinear hydrodynamic bodies, passive yawing, batch simulations, and more. This flexibility makes WEC-Sim a versatile tool adaptable to numerous applications within the wave energy sector.

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Through input from a broad user base and an extensive team of developers and collaborators, a suite of WEC-Sim applications cases has been created and is available open-source. The WEC-Sim Applications repository includes readily available and easy to use examples pertaining to mechanical and electrical power generation from WECs, mooring systems, generalized modes, desalination, cables, and many other specialized use cases desalination. Recent WEC-Sim Applications demonstrate and document the application of WEC-Sim for advanced control implementation and hybrid systems.

Since its initial release in December 2014, WEC-Sim v1.0 has seen substantial growth in its user base, becoming a widely used tool for numerical modeling of various wave energy converter (WEC) devices. It has even found applications beyond wave energy. The user map illustrates the global adoption of WEC-Sim. Moreover, a literature review has documented over 139 publications featuring WEC-Sim between 2015 and 2023, as shown in Fig 1. While early publications were mainly produced by NREL and SNL, there has been a rise in external research contributions to conferences and journals in recent years.

The WEC-Sim v6.0 release introduces a range of significant enhancements and new features. This version includes large XY displacement options, the amplitude spectra function, customizable degrees of freedom for plotBEMIO, and the calculation of added masses using radiationIRF.m. Tutorials and documentation have been comprehensively updated, especially for control applications and advanced features. Key updates include the integration of BEMIOH5 for pressure integration and improvements to Morison element implementation.

Additional updates feature the normalization of quaternions, compatibility with Capytaine v2 for hydrostatics, and enhanced Paraview features and documentation. The release also includes a simple direct drive PTO model, improved control and PTO documentation, and the implementation of an FIR filter for radiation forces, further extending WEC-Sim's capabilities. Finally, the transition to MoorDyn v2 marks another significant advancement in this version.

In WEC-Sim Applications v6.0, a breadth of advanced controls applications demonstrates and can guide users on implementing a variety of controls systems in WEC-Sim including passive, reactive, declutching, latching and model predictive controllers. Another new application highlights how a load mitigating feedback control can be implemented in WEC-Sim.

Throughout 2023, Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) and the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) collaborated with the MOREnergy Lab at the Polytechnic University of Turin, Italy to incorporate the capabilities of the MATLAB OFWT Simulation Tool (MOST) [3] for modeling offshore floating wind turbine (OFWT) systems. In v6.0 of WEC-Sim, WEC-Sim and MOST are combined and can simulate both platform hydrodynamics and horizontal axis wind turbine aerodynamics simultaneously, enabling hybrid-renewable energy systems modeling. A new application demonstrates using WEC-Sim+MOST to model a floating IEA 15MW reference wind turbine with the VoltornUS-S semisubmersible platform. In this abstract, we focus on the advanced controls applications features and the WEC-Sim/MOST coupling. In this paper the applications related to MoorDyn, MOST and Advanced Controls will be discussed.

2. WEC-Sim Applications: Advanced controls:

The performance of a wave energy converter (WEC) in generating power is significantly influenced by the choice of control algorithm deployed within the system. Various control strategies have been extensively researched and applied in marine energy applications. These algorithms can either directly manipulate power take-off (PTO) components to achieve specific outputs or operate as high-level controllers focused on managing the overall PTO force applied to the WEC.

In this context, the examples highlighted emphasize the use of high-level controller applications. WEC-Sim incorporates features supporting a spectrum of control strategies, ranging from basic passive and reactive controllers to more sophisticated methods like model predictive control (MPC).

In WEC-Sim Applications v6.0, the software facilitates numerical simulations of a semi-submerged sphere with a diameter of 10 meters, utilizing a diverse array of controllers: declutching, latching, model predictive control (MPC), passive damping (P), and reactive control (PI). Each controller example within these simulations features dedicated functions designed to calculate optimal control parameters based on detailed hydrodynamic coefficients. These

Fig 1. WEC-Sim Citations over the period 2015-2023

functions are designed to be versatile and applicable across a wide range of wave energy converter (WEC) designs. This capability empowers users to rigorously test and optimize their own custom-designed WEC configurations within the WEC-Sim framework.

These controllers play a crucial role in the optimization and performance of wave energy converters (WECs) due to their specific functionalities:

Passive Damping (P): Provides passive control and is easy to manufacture and cheap to deploy. The passive control is a damping control with an optimum damping coefficient “ c ” of [4]:

$$c = \sqrt{B(\omega)^2 + \left(\frac{K_h}{\omega} - \omega(m + A(\omega))\right)^2}$$

Where ω , m , $B(\omega)$, K_h , and $A(\omega)$ are the wave frequency, the buoy mass radiation damping, hydrostatic stiffness, and hydrodynamic added mass respectively. In which the control force is defined as:

$$F_{pto} = -c\dot{x}$$

Reactive Control (PI): Implements proportional-integral control algorithm to adjust power take-off (PTO) coefficients to achieve system mechanical impedance matching (resonance) [5], in which the damping

$$K_p = B(\omega)$$

$$K_i = (m + A(\omega))\omega^2 + K_h$$

Where K_p and K_i are the proportional and integral parts, and the control force becomes:

$$F_{pto} = -K_p\dot{x} - K_i x$$

Latching: A form of damping control in which the WEC is allowed to move freely at certain times at latched with a large damping at other times. By doing this, the device is forced slow down such that its motion becomes in phase with the incident waves. The large damping force is achieved by using a damping force calculated as [6]:

$$c = 80(m + A(\omega))$$

And the optimal latching time is expressed as:

$$t_{latch} = \frac{1}{2}(T_{wave} + T_n)$$

Where T_{wave} is the wave particular period, $T_n = \frac{\omega_n}{2\pi}$ and ω_n is the device natural frequency.

Declutching: It is another damping control methodology that is opposite to latching. Estimating the optimal declutching time and damping values is more complex than for latching. The device’s motion depends on its impedance during declutching, so it doesn’t move entirely freely. Unlike optimal latching, the declutching time is assumed to be about half the difference between the natural period and the wave period such that:

$$t_{declutch} = \frac{1}{2}(T_{wave} - T_n)$$

Model Predictive Control (MPC): Utilizes predictive models to optimize energy capture by anticipating wave conditions and dynamically adjusting control parameters in real-time.

These controllers are essential as they enable WECs to operate effectively in unpredictable marine environments, optimizing energy extraction while ensuring structural integrity and operational safety. Their versatility allows for adaptation to different WEC designs and environmental conditions, making them invaluable tools for advancing the feasibility and viability of wave energy as a renewable energy source.

3. MoorDyn Coupling:

MoorDyn is a lumped-mass solver created by NREL for simulating the mooring dynamics of offshore structures. Its C++ version, MoorDyn-C, offers adaptability for various applications and integrations [7]. MoorDyn-C can be compiled as a dynamically-linked library and is compatible with Python, Fortran, and Matlab through respective modules. It includes simplified functions to facilitate integration with models or scripts written in C/C++, Fortran, Matlab/Simulink, and more, and it supports coupling with WEC-Sim.

The integration of WEC-Sim with MoorDyn has been upgraded to use MoorDyn-C v2 while maintaining compatibility with the MoorDyn v1 API. This new feature allows users to specify the path and file name for the

MoorDyn input file, ensuring it matches the output file path. This enhancement ensures that the performance remains consistent with the previous MoorDyn v1 coupling and facilitates the future use of MoorDyn v2 features.

4. MOST v1.0.0 (within WEC-Sim v 6.0):

Matlab for Floating Offshore wind turbine (MOST) is a nonlinear time domain modeling tool designed to simulate offshore floating wind. MOST evaluates the turbine's movement in six degrees of freedom, power production, and blade load cycles. The aerodynamics are modeled using blade element momentum theory, while the hydrodynamics are modeled with WEC-Sim. Simscape's flexibility allows for the rapid introduction of complex dynamic systems, including hybrid wave-wind platforms, flexible platforms, and sea water active ballast systems. MOST's results are compared with FAST in [8]. The case study involves a 15 MW reference wind turbine on the Voltorn US platform, showing good agreement between the two models and significantly reduced simulation time.

Acknowledgements:

Sandia National Laboratories is a multimission laboratory managed and operated by National Technology & Engineering Solutions of Sandia, LLC, a wholly owned subsidiary of Honeywell International Inc., for the U.S. Department of Energy's National Nuclear Security Administration under contract DE-NA0003525. This work was authored in part by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory, operated by Alliance for Sustainable Energy, LLC, for the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) under Contract No. DE-AC36-08GO28308.

References:

- [1] "WEC-Sim." Accessed: Jun. 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/WEC-Sim/WEC-Sim/tree/v6.0>
- [2] "WEC-Sim Applications." Accessed: Jun. 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/WEC-Sim/WEC-Sim/tree/v6.0>
- [3] "MatLab for OFWT Simulation Tools." Accessed: Jun. 13, 2024. [Online]. Available: http://www.moreenergylab.polito.it/most_13122023/
- [4] R. P. F. Gomes, M. F. P. Lopes, J. C. C. Henriques, L. M. C. Gato, and A. F. O. Falcão, "The dynamics and power extraction of bottom-hinged plate wave energy converters in regular and irregular waves," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 96, pp. 86–99, 2015, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2014.12.024>.
- [5] R. G. Coe, G. Bacelli, and D. Forbush, "A practical approach to wave energy modeling and control," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 142, p. 110791, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110791>.
- [6] A. Babarit and A. H. Clément, "Optimal latching control of a wave energy device in regular and irregular waves," *Applied Ocean Research*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 77–91, 2006, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apor.2006.05.002>.
- [7] "<https://www.nrel.gov/wind/nwtc/moordyn.html>," <https://www.nrel.gov/wind/nwtc/moordyn.html>.
- [8] M. Sirigu, E. Faraggiana, A. Ghigo, and G. Bracco, "Development of MOST, a fast simulation model for optimisation of floating offshore wind turbines in Simscape Multibody," *J Phys Conf Ser*, vol. 2257, no. 1, p. 12003, Apr. 2022, doi: [10.1088/1742-6596/2257/1/012003](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2257/1/012003).